

Pi, phi and e in Khafre's dimensions

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Abstract

Some formulas showing how approximations for pi, phi and e are in the dimensions of Khafre.

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1. Introduction

“The language of Giza is mathematics.”

Robert Bauval

“You will believe.”

The architects of Giza

Many people have discussed the approximations for π , φ and e inherent in Khufu's dimensions. These same numbers can also be found in Khafre, and introduce mathematical functions that the 4th dynasty has not documented.

2. Notation, accuracy and methodology

2.1 Notation

I take the royal cubit as $\pi/6$ metres, to 4 decimal places. (*The Beautiful Cubit System*, Douglas 2019 [1]). While working on ZTM101 last year it became apparent they thought 3 or 4 decimals were accurate enough, so I have used that, and things “just work.”

Symbols used in this and other papers:

Symbol	Name	Approximate / practical value	% Accuracy to true
π	Archimedes' constant	3.1416	99.9998
e	Euler's number	2.7183	99.9993
φ	Golden ratio	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
Ⓔ	Royal cubit aka cubit	0.5236m ($\pi/6$)	99.9998

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I use “cubit” for Royal cubit Ⓔ.

3. Phi

This chapter in my ongoing exploration of Giza started when I got to wondering if phi was also lurking somewhere in Khafre. Khafre is based on the classic Pythagorean 3:4:5 right triangle, so it seemed unlikely that φ could be lurking there, but my guides began to insist. So I began to look.

After trying many things, I eventually stumbled on the answer, cleverly hidden. It is this: The sphere that has the same volume as Khafre, has a diameter of almost 100φ metres. It's the closest you can get while maintaining the 3:4:5 ratio.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pyramid Volume} &= \frac{\text{base} \times \text{height}}{3} = \frac{411^2 \times 274}{3} = 15,428,118 \text{ Ⓔ}^2 \\ \text{Convert to metres}^3 & \\ 15,428,118 \times 0.5236^3 &= 2,214,684.497 \text{ m}^3 \\ \text{Volume of sphere} &= \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \\ \therefore 2,214,684.497 &= \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \\ \therefore r^3 &= \frac{3 \times 2,214,684.497}{4 \pi} \\ \therefore r &= \sqrt[3]{528,715.7412} \\ \therefore r &= 80.8613 \\ \therefore \text{diameter} &= 161.7226 \approx 100 \varphi \end{aligned}$$

The accuracy to 100φ is 99.95%.

4. e

I had no sooner found this, when my guides asked, “And what about e?”

Suffice to say that that resulted in a major disagreement ... my view was that they were messing with my head and generally being impossible.

I tried a few things and got nowhere.

I tried more things and had sleepless nights and still got nowhere, although I did find a few curiosities like $220 + 411 \approx 100\rho e$.

They kept insisting, and the only clue I could get was that it is all “self-contained.”

Finally, it surfaced. I had to apologise... they were right, and I was wrong ... again.

The implications (and also for π , up next), are profound and deeply disturbing.

$$411 \times \sqrt{\varphi} = 411 \times \sqrt{1.618} = 522.7945849$$

$$\log_{10}(522.7945849) = 2.718331081$$

The accuracy to e is 99.998%.

5. Pi

While I was still recovering from this, they asked, “And pi?”

Having learnt my lesson, I put up less of a fight while still remaining sceptical.

After some other close approximations with the plastic ratio, the real secret emerged.

$$\frac{411 \times \varphi^2}{2} = \frac{411 \times 2.618}{2} = 537.999$$

$$\frac{\ln(537.999)}{2} = \frac{6.287856701}{2} = 3.143928351$$

The accuracy to π is 99.9257%.

6. Anything better?

These relationships raise the question: is this by chance, or design?

To answer that, I wrote a short program to check every possible combination for base and height between 1 and 1000 €. The only requirement was that the pyramid should be a 3:4:5 pyramid.

I then computed the ratios for φ , e and π as above, to find which pyramid gave the most accurate

average. That found the current 411×274 to be the best, with an average accuracy of 99.958%.

So where does that leave us? This is a major nod towards logarithms, in both base 10 and e, which the 4th dynasty is not supposed to know about. Similarly, the volume of a sphere is credited to Archimedes.

7. Acknowledgements

Thanks as always to my “guides,” whoever or whatever they are, for their constant prompting and odd ideas, which frequently lead to shocking discoveries and amazed laughter. I wish I knew them.

Thanks to the team behind the Libertinus fonts [2].

8. Bibliography

- [1] Douglas, Ian, ‘The Beautiful Cubit System’. Jun. 30, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3263864>
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